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Capturing football-teams behaviour with a Markov model

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ABSTRACT

This thesis aims to capture soccer teams behavior using a stochastic approach on a graph built on top of the Wyscout dataset, a market-leading company in data scouting for soccer. The main contributions of the thesis are twofold: first, it proposes a stochastic representation of a soccer game via a weighted graph properly derived from the Wyscout dataset. Secondly, it analyses every game through a Markov model to detect the way teams move the ball together with the way they move onto the field and the performance that they achieve.

INTRODUCTION

Systematic analysis of sports has been performed since the 1950s by means of manual notation methods [45]. However human observation can be unreliable, experimental results of this study [21] shows that the recollection of significant game events performed by expert observers is as low as 42%.

Moreover, human observation is not able to analyze the huge number of games played every week.

Until a few years ago there was no viable alternative and scouting was forced to rely on human observers.

The improvements in electronics allowed the design of both optical and device tracking systems. Such systems generate a huge amount of raw data that is impossible to analyze manually.

The rise of Artificial Intelligence led to the development of automated (or semi-automated in some cases) labeling algorithms that convert the raw data produced by these systems into a more abstract and human-readable form.

These systems allowed the creation of huge spatio-temporal datasets. Given the availability of such datasets, sports science literature proliferated and a lot of automated systems to perform systematic analyses of sports were born.

The goal of this thesis is to build an automated framework for the tactic analysis of football games.

To build such a framework we first define the behavior of football teams. Then we design a methodology that outputs a weighted graph that implements a stochastic representation of teams from event-log datasets, such as the Wyscout one available for this study.

This way our graphs are simple to visualize, interpret and analyze and, moreover, allow to use the huge amount of graph algorithms already present in the literature.

The weighted graph is generated by dividing the field into different regions by means of a fully data-driven approach. The movements of the ball recorded in the dataset are converted into weighted edges. More precisely events are divided into offensive and defensive. Events that move the ball from one region to another are offensive, while events that stop the ball are defensive.

Offensive events are modeled as edges while defensive ones are

modeled as self-loops, the weight of each edge is the likelihood of the occurrence of the corresponding event.

Besides the teams, we also model games as graphs by merging the graphs of the two teams facing each other.

To analyze different issues of the behavior of teams, we develop three different models defined as follows:

- **The flow model** that models the most frequent sequences of passes occurring in football games.
- **The distribution model** that models the distribution of played events during a game.
- **The score model** that predicts the winner of football games.

To validate the results of these models we develop several baselines which have been trained and tested on three seasons of the Italian Serie A.

Our model predicts the most frequent sequences and the winners of the games with a high-level accuracy but fails to predict the distribution of events.

RELATED WORK

Some of the open problems in sports science literature are the evaluation of both team and players performance and the prediction of future events occurring during games.

To solve these problems, many studies build tools and abstractions that are the input of more complex algorithmic and probabilistic analysis of team sports.

Since the spatial information contained in the datasets is low level and contains some errors, it is common to discretize the playing area into regions and assign the location points contained in the dataset to them. There are different ways to discretize the pitch. In the literature, rectangles of equal size [2, 5, 8, 21, 36, 39, 47] and hand-designed grids [7, 24, 37] are the most utilized. We decided to not use uniform grids since they do not respect the distribution of events. Hand-designed grids, instead, bias data since they are designed by humans.

To respect the distribution of events and not to bias the data we utilize a fully data driven approach to divide the football pitch into regions via an unsupervised machine learning algorithm.

Another way to partition the pitch is to divide it into dominant regions, which are the ones that a player can reach before any other player [23, 26, 38, 48]. Dominant regions are not suited for our study since they are more useful to evaluate player performance than team behavior.

Besides the playing area subdivision, complex networks are often built on top of these datasets. Two types of networks are commonly used for this kind of analysis: **passing networks** and **transition networks**.

In the literature, passing networks are the most frequently used, they are defined as a graph $G=(V,E)$ where each player is modeled as a node and two nodes v_1 and v_2 in V have a directed edge $e = (v_1, v_2)$ from v_1 to v_2 with integer weight $w(e)$ such that the player represented by node v_1 has made $w(e)$ successful passes to the player represented by node v_2 [43]. Transition networks are passing networks extended with additional nodes that models outcomes.

The difference between such networks and the ones that we use in this thesis is that we abstract from players; the nodes of our network are regions of the field. We aim to analyze teams as

complex systems by studying the cooperation between players. The most common analysis performed on these networks is the centrality [12, 13, 17, 20, 25, 44] which is mostly used to identify key players.

In this thesis, we also compute a centrality measure by means of PageRank. In our case, we do not use PageRank to identify key players, but we used it to compute which are the most important regions for a team and the probability of them scoring a goal.

The representations and structure described above are informative in isolation, thus they are used to perform some analysis, but they are also the input of more complex analyses of team sports.

Sports analysts can judge events and situations that occur during a game and apply qualitative attributes, for example, they are able to rate the risk of a shot or the quality of a pass. Horton et al. [27] presented a classifier that rates the quality of passes in football matches by applying a label of *good*, *OK* or *bad* to each pass, achieving an accuracy rate of 85.8%.

Bialkowski et al. [2] examine whether lineups could accurately predict the play style of a football team. Their learned model is able to identify the playing style of teams by exploiting features, which describe their lineups, and thus achieving an accuracy of 67.23%.

In our study, we use a completely different approach to predict teams playing styles, since instead of utilizing the lineups we exploit the distribution of the events and the interactions between players.

Wei et al. [55] built a model to make short-term predictions of which football player will be in possession of the ball after a given interval, achieving an accuracy of 99.25%.

Kim et al. [29] model the evolution of football events from the trajectories of the players to predict the location of the ball at a point in the near future.

In our study instead, we predict the distribution of events to compute the likelihood of finding the ball in some particular regions of the football field.

In their research, [5, 7] identify commonly occurring sequences of passes between players in football matches. Their approach is different from ours because we identify commonly occurring sequences of passes between regions instead of players. They also use the temporal information in their model, while our graph does not include this information.

Research in [26, 53] aims to detect frequently occurring sequences of passes between players by means of a suffix tree. Given two values v and t , they are able to compute all sequences of passes of length v that occurred at least t times.

Our flow model is able answer a similar query, which is given a length l and a value v , it can return the v most common sequences of passes of length l .

Van Haaren et al. [51] face the problem of finding patterns in offensive football strategies, by means of inductive logic programming. The result is a set of rules describing the frequently occurring interaction sequences.

The results that they achieve are similar to the one provided by the flow model. They both identify sequences of passes between regions of the football pitch, but they exploit two different approaches since we use a graph analysis and they use inductive logic programming.

DATASET

Modern sports games are represented using spatio-temporal data, the defining characteristic of this data is that it is a sequence of samples containing a time-stamp and the location of some phenomena.

In case of team sports, two types of spatio-temporal data are commonly captured: *object trajectories* that capture the movement of players or the ball, and *events logs* that record the location and time of events.

OBJECT TRAJECTORIES. The movements of players or the ball inside the playing area are sampled as a sequence of time-stamp and location points in the plane.

To capture this data, *optical tracking systems* or *device tracking systems* are used [14, 28, 32, 35]. *Optical tracking systems* use fixed cameras to record videos of the player movement, the images are then processed to compute the trajectories. Usually, these kinds of systems quantify player's movement, distance, velocity and acceleration during match-play but, they do not allow on-the-ball events to be recorded. There is one system, whose performance is studied in [6], that records both types of information.

EVENT LOGS. Event logs are a sequence of significant events that occur during a match. In football, players originate events by interacting with the ball. Event logs are different from object trajectories because they are not dense, samples are captured only when an event occurs, however they are more expressive in the capture of details like the type of event and the players involved. There are several commercial vendors that supply event logs dataset, in case of football data the main are [34] and [56].

WYSCOUT DATASET. The dataset used in our experiments is event log based, it is provided by **Wyscout** (<https://wyscout.com>), a market-leading company in data scouting for soccer. It contains 1138 games, 1372506 events generated by 1144 players

from the seasons 2014, 2015, 2016 of the Italian Serie A. Each game, in the dataset, consists of a sequence of events with some additional meta-data. These events are generated by the interaction between players and ball so, there is no information about players away from the ball. In this scenario, the game looks like a sampling of the position of the ball over time. The meta-data present are:

- **date**: when the game was played.
- **home_team**: the team playing in home.
- **away_team**: the team playing away.

Then there is the list of events generated during the game. Each event records:

- **outcome**: the result of the events chosen from a fixed set.
- **player**: the player generating the event by interacting with the ball.
- **position**: where (on the field) the event is generated.
- **team**: the team of the player.
- **time**: seconds passed from the kick-off.
- **type**: event type chosen from a fixed set.

Position captures where the event happened. The field size is expressed in percentage from 0 to 100; (0,50) and (100,50) corresponds to the two goals, (50,50) to the midfield. The home team attacks always from left to right and the away from right to left. This way each field appears of size 100×100 .

Possible values for the outcome are:

- **save**: save by the goalkeeper (only him no other player).
- **catch**: goalkeeper grabs the ball.
- **punch**: goalkeeper punches the ball away.
- **blocked**: shot intercepted by one player, not necessarily the goalkeeper.
- **goal**: shot that results in a goal.
- **off_target**: shots out of the goal.

- **wood_work**: shots on the post or on the crossbar.
- **success, Success, completed, Completed**: event completed with success. This does not apply to shots.
- **failed, Failed**: event failed, in these cases, the ball is intercepted. This does not apply to shots.
- **failedclearance**: a player failed to throw the ball away.
- **failedcatch**: the goalkeeper failed to grab the ball.
- **headed**: a player hits the ball with the head.
- **clearance**: a player throws the ball away.
- **Assist**: pass that creates the possibility of scoring.
- **Fouled, Foul**: a player commits a foul.
- **aerialFoul**: a player commits an aerial foul.

Possible events are:

- **save**: when the goalkeeper saves a shot.
- **shot**: a player shoots the ball.
- **aerial**: a player hits the ball with the head.
- **pass_block**: pass blocked by a player
- **throw_away**: ball thrown away by a player.
- **pass**: a player pass the ball to another player.
- **tackles**: a player tackle another player.
- **crosses**: a player crosses the ball.
- **corners**: a player kicks the corner.
- **takeons**: a player dribbles another player.
- **fouls**: a player commits foul.
- **cards**: a player receive a card.

The original dataset consisted in a set of *json* files. Json files are plain text files containing a key:value map. Listing 1 shows an example of a json file.

```

1 "date": "Sun,,12,Apr,2015",
2 "home_team": 15,
3 "away_team": 6,
4 "events": [{"playerId": 69, "timestamp": 3690, "teamId": 6,
  "position": ["0,50"], "outcome": "save", "type":
  "save"}, ...]

```

Listing 1: Example of a json file

The description above shows some inconsistencies present inside the dataset. There are some repetitions like success, Success, Completed and some overlaps between types and outcomes. To solve this problem and have a consistent view, the dataset is normalized by dropping some information (or storing them somewhere else), sorting the event list by time, removing some repetitions, and memorizing the sequence of events in *Comma-Separated Values* (csv) files. The choice of using the csv format was taken because they are more readable (for this particular application), also a tabular storage is easier to navigate and to operate upon. An example of the resulting files can be found in Table 1.

Figure 1 shows the richness of information captured in a single

Figure 1: Events generated during a single match, the attacking direction is from left to right. The events are plotted where they occur.

match. The events are not equally distributed over the field, there are some zones that are denser than others. Most of the events are passes but there are some tackles, clearances, shots, and crosses and they are distributed differently in different zones.

Table 1: Example of dataset

outcome	playerId	position	team	time	type
completed	199	[(50.5,51.1), (50.9,50.5)]	6	1	pass
completed	457	[(50.9,50.2), (41.6,50.1)]	6	2	pass
completed	263	[(41.6,50.1), (31.0,38.6)]	6	4	pass
completed	484	[(31.3,38.6), (31.3,76.9)]	6	6	pass
completed	445	[(44.5,82), (53.5,96.8)]	6	12	pass
completed	92	[(55.9,96.6), (41.0,85.5)]	6	16	pass
completed	445	[(40.4,82.5), (35.0,40.4)]	6	19	pass
failed	484	[(44.8,38.5), (68.7,56.7)]	6	24	pass
	68	[(28.8,43.1)]	15	26	aerial
completed	68	[(26.2,42.9), (27.2,69.0)]	15	28	pass
completed	541	[(27.2,69), (37.3,69.9)]	15	31	pass
completed	294	[(37.3,69.9), (25.9,85.0)]	15	32	pass
failed	643	[(25.9,85), (72.0,88.7)]	15	34	pass
completed	484	[(22.9,14.7), (4.2,30.1)]	6	39	pass
completed	69	[(4.2,30.1), (14.4,63.9)]	6	40	pass
completed	445	[(14.4,63.9), (23.7,51.7)]	6	43	pass
completed	263	[(23.7,51.7), (4.5,44.2)]	6	45	pass
5completed	69	[(4.5,44.2), (13.2,79.6)]	6	47	pass
completed	445	[(14.2,74.5), (20.7,70.2)]	6	50	pass
completed	263	[(20.7,70.2), (15.6,78.2)]	6	52	pass
completed	445	[(15.6,78.2), (38.2,96.8)]	6	53	pass
completed	31	[(42.9,85.8), (47.2,65.2)]	6	57	pass
completed	57	[(47.2,65.2), (42.3,71.7)]	6	59	pass
failed	263	[(42.3,71.7), (64.5,34.4)]	6	61	pass
headed	643	[(29.6,63.1)]	15	63	clearance
failed	484	[(39.8,32.5), (100.0,5.5)]	6	65	pass
failed	263	[(34.1,78.3), (53.7,83.4)]	6	100	pass
failed	68	[(44.6,31.2), (55.7,22.1)]	15	101	pass
completed	31	[(45.8,81.2), (53.8,73.9)]	6	102	pass
Failed	181	[(42.6,29.8)]	6	105	tackles
Success	57	[(57.4,70.2)]	6	105	takeons

GRAPHS

The main idea is to model a football game as a stochastic process. Since states and transitions of a process can be visualized as a directed graph, this chapter will explain how to build such a graph. The connection with stochastic processes and the analysis performed will be explained in chapter 3.

As described in chapter 1, games are sequences of events. To derive a graph out of them a method to map events into nodes, edges, and self-loop was developed.

2.1 PLAYING AREA SUBDIVISION

The spatial information contained in the dataset are low level. Analyzing and interpreting these data is very difficult. These data contain some errors, and indeed the precision is not very high. Moreover, spatial data are very sparse and any analysis performed directly on them does not achieve statistical significance.

To achieve statistical significance and filter out the errors, it is common to discretize the playing area into regions and assign the location points contained in the dataset to one of them.

There are different ways to discretize the pitch. A common approach, adopted in [2, 5, 8, 21, 36, 39, 47], is to divide the playing area into rectangles of equal size. However, Figure 1 shows that the event distribution is not uniform in the playing area. Thus, this approach will create regions of different densities. Some regions will contain more events and others fewer events.

In solving this problem, some known studies [7, 24, 37] divide the playing area by means of a hand designed grid, with rectangles aligned with the penalty box. Designing regions with arbitrary size allow giving the correct emphasis to each region if the importance of each of them is known a priori. However, this approach introduces a bias inside the discretization, some regions might be considered more important than others even if they are not.

Other approaches, such as **movement models** and **dominant regions** introduced by Taki et al [48] and its variations [23, 26, 38] are utilized to estimate both players and teams performance

[50]. But, the computation of the dominant regions requires the complete tracking of all players during the game; the event-log database available for this study does not contain the necessary information.

Figure 2: Pitch subdivision in 9 regions, the attacking direction is from left to right

In this study, a subdivision is considered "good" if it is easily interpretable, with respect to the distribution of the events, and takes into account spatial similarity between events. Subdivisions that respect these requirements model data correctly because they give the right importance to each region, they avoid that uncorrelated events are grouped together, and they give useful information from a football point of view. Since both uniform grids and hand-designed ones do not respect these requirements or bias the data, the ones utilized in this study are derived utilizing a unsupervised learning, data-driven approach which is fully data driven.

In data science, clustering algorithms provide a way of grouping a set of objects, in such a way that objects in the same group (also known as cluster), are more similar to each other than to those in other groups.

In our studied case, the algorithm used is **Kmeans** [33]. There are others algorithms that are better density estimators like **Db-scan** [19], but differently from kmeans, they may find not convex clusters, which are not interpretable to model a zone of

Figure 3: Silhouette measured, on the x-axis is present the number of clusters

the pitch where players may be located and play. Also, convex clusters can be represented as Voronoi cells, this representation is really simple to plot on a football pitch, thus it is easily understood from a football point of view. Moreover, kmeans guarantees that each region contains almost, the same amount of events thus, it does not over-emphasize or under-emphasize some regions. Figure 2 shows an example of a pitch divided in 9 regions.

Kmeans takes in input the number of clusters in which the objects are divided. This raises the problem of deciding the number of regions contained in the subdivision. To address this problem we introduce the following definition [46]:

$$\text{silhouette}(p) = \frac{b(p) - a(p)}{\max\{a(p), b(p)\}} \quad (1)$$

where:

- p is a generic point.
- $a(p)$ is the average distance between point i and all other points within the same cluster.
- $b(p)$ is the smallest average distance of point i to all points in any other cluster.

The silhouette score refers to a method of interpretation and validation of consistency within clusters of data. Equation 1 shows the formula used to compute it. Figure 3 shows the silhouette measured by dividing the field from 4 to 42 regions.

In this case, silhouette did not give any useful indication on the optimal number of zones since the score oscillates from ≈ 0.33 to ≈ 0.37 . These variations are too small to assess the optimal number of regions.

Since silhouette did not help in deciding the optimal number of zones, the Sum of **Sum of Squared Errors** (SSE) [49] was calculated.

$$SSE = \sum_{i=1}^k \sum_{p \in C_i} (\vec{p} - \vec{m}_i)^2 \quad (2)$$

where:

- k number of clusters.
- C_i the set of points in cluster i.
- m_i the center point of cluster i.

Figure 4 shows the SSE measured on the same subdivision used before. In this case, there is a minor change of slope in 11 nodes but, it is not meaningful, other values can be used as well.

The number of zones is limited to 42 because subdivision in more than 42 zones become unreadable and the average number of events inside a game is between 1000-2000 thus, subdivisions with more than 25 regions contain very few events for each zone.

Figure 5 and 6 show that some subdivisions are not symmetric, meaning that in average teams originate more events on one side of the field.

Since none of the metrics gave indications on which is the optimal number of zones, all of them are kept. The number of zones is a parameter of the model and the following analysis will study how the model performs by varying the number of zones.

Figure 4: Sum of squared errors (SSE) measured, on the x axis is present the number of clusters

Figure 5: Example of asymmetric nodes detection

Figure 6: Example of symmetric nodes detection

2.2 BALL FLOW MODELLING

The main goal of this study is to capture the football teams behavior. The behavior is the way teams move the ball. As described in Chapter 1, the events-log dataset used for this study contains the position of the ball before and after each event. Information like the origin or the end of passes or crosses are not directly available but they are obtained performing few preprocessing steps.

Since movements of the ball can be visualized as edges from one region to another; from now on, these movements are called edges. There are two kinds of edges, as showed in Figure 7, the

Figure 7: Possible types of edges.

ones that connect two nodes and self-edges that connect a node to itself.

Preprocessing. The first step is filtering out not interesting events from the dataset; the ones that do not influence the ball directly. For example yellow/red cards are removed. Table 1 shows the information contained inside each events. In particular, the tag position contains origin and end coordinates of the event. Exploiting the subdivision described before, these coordinates are converted to regions. The original events are quintuples containing (*start position, end position, type, outcome, team*). These quintuples are converted into other quintuples containing (*start region, end region, type, outcome, team*) .

Classification. Events are divided in two categories: **offensive** and **defensive**. The criteria used to classify events to these categories is: "*if the event tries to stop the action is declared defensive, offensive in all other cases*". The complete offensive/defensive mapping can be found in Table 2.

In general, events like passes and crosses move the ball from

Offensive	Defensive
Pass	Save
Shot	Pass-block
Take-on	Tackle
Clearance	Aerial
Cross	Foul
Corner	

Table 2: Events classification

one region to another, thus they are classified as offensive. Since, tackles and fouls stop the ball in one region they are classified as defensive. In a football game, the attacking team tries to score the goal while the other team attempts to stop it. Thus, defensive events are modeled as self-loops, because they stall the ball, which will be in the same position after the event. Offensive ones, instead are modeled as edges connecting different zones since they move the ball.

Edge recognition. Edge recognition is not as straightforward as it appears, given the structure of the data; events contain information about when the ball arrives at a player and when it leaves its feet. Origin and end of passes and crosses are not directly available, thus they have to be derived. The way in which this information is gathered is to analyze events in pairs and correlating the information.

The way to gather information about the movements of the ball is shown in Algorithm 1.

The algorithm starts by removing all failed tackles (and pass_block) from the sequence of events and assigning them to the defensive team (line 3). This first step is needed to remove the correlation between far events. Sometimes there is a pass event that is completed with success but before reaching the other player of the same team an opponent tries to intercept it without success. This means that in case of a completed pass is not enough to observe the next event but it is necessary to check the successive events until either a completed tackle or an event generated by a player of the same team is found.

This approach is less efficient than scanning the dataset once, filtering out these events and checking only the successive event in case of the offensive ones.

The second step is to analyze the events, at this point three situations are possible:

1. A shoot is found (line 5-11).
2. An offensive event is found (12-15).
3. A defensive event is found (16-17).

In the first case, three other sub-cases are possible: a goal is scored, the goalkeeper saves, the shoot is off target. In all these cases, a shoot is added to the offending team (line 8), then if a goal is scored it is taken into account (line 10), this information is used by the score model presented in Chapter 3 to compute the weight of the offensive edge that connects goalkeeper and goal; if the goalkeeper saves a save is given to the defending team (line 12); off-target shots do not give any other information.

In case of finding offensive events, an edge from the origin to the end of the event is added (line 16), this accounts for the movement of the ball performed by the player. Then, if the offensive event is successful (the ball is still in possession of the same team) another edge is added from the end of the current event to the beginning of the next event (line 18). This accounts for the movement of the ball given by passes or crosses.

In case of a defensive event, only a self-loop is generated (line 20).

The final part of the algorithm (line 21-34) is to analyze the last event and add the corresponding edge. This edge should be treated separately because it is not possible to correlate it with future events since there are not.

Algorithm 1 Edge recognition

Input:

E sequence of events.

Output:

S list of edges.

```
1: function GATHER_EDGES(E)
2:   S  $\leftarrow$   $\emptyset$ 
3:   Remove from E all failed tackles and insert into S as
   defensive events
4:   for i  $\leftarrow$  0 to |E| - 1 do
5:     if E[i].type = shot then
6:       Recover the offending team
7:       Recover the defending team
8:       Add the shoot to the offending team
9:       if E[i].outcome == goal then
10:        Add the goal to the offending team
11:      else if E[i].outcome == save then
12:        Add the save to the defending team
13:      else if E[i].outcome == off_target then
14:        do nothing
15:      else if isOffensive(E[i].type) then
16:        Add Edge(E[i].end, E[i+1].origin) to S[E[i].team]
17:      if E[i].team = E[i + 1].team then
18:        Add Edge(E[i].origin, E[i].end) to S[E[i].team]
19:      else if isDefensive(E[i].type) then
20:        Add SelfEdge(E[i].end, E[i+1].origin) to S[E[i].team]
21:    if E.last().type = shot then
22:      Recover the offending team
23:      Recover the defending team
24:      Add the shoot to the offending team
25:      if E.last().outcome == goal then
26:        Add the goal to the offending team
27:      else if E.last().outcome == save then
28:        Add the save to the defending team
29:      else if E[i].outcome == off_target then
30:        do nothing
31:      else if isOffensive(E.last().type) then
32:        Add Edge(E.last().end, E.last().origin) to S[E.last().team]
33:      else if isDefensive(E.last().type) then
34:        Add SelfEdge(E.last().end, E.last().origin) to S[E.last().team]
```

2.3 BUILDING THE GRAPH

The information gathered above are utilized to build a graph. A graph, as showed in Equation 3, is a finite set V called vertex set and a finite, binary relation E on V called edge set. .

$$\text{Graph} = (V, E) \quad (3)$$

where:

- V finite set of vertex (nodes).
- E finite set of pairs of vertex called edges.

Nodes represents region of the football field. These regions are derived utilizing the playing area subdivision discussed before. Since nodes are derived by utilizing all spatial data inside the dataset, they are the same for all teams. Furthermore, having the same nodes allows comparing different graphs. Instead of showing the regions, for readability, nodes are visualized centered on the centroid of each region.

Edges capture the movement of the ball from region to region. They are derived using the recognition procedure illustrated before. Differently, to the nodes, they are team independent; meaning that each team has its own edges. Each edge contains a weight. This weight is the edge traversal frequency.

MODEL AND ANALYSIS

Zaccaro et al. [57] define teams as a group of individuals working collaboratively and in a coordinated manner towards a common goal be it winning a game, increasing productivity, or increasing a common good. Football players are extremely cooperative; Pappalardo et al. [42] show that football games contain 1700 events on average, and 72% of them are passes. Capturing the interactions between individuals is a central goal of social network analysis [54] thus, in sports science literature, team sports are often analyzed by means of complex network tools. Cooperation between players is influenced by multiple causes that produce multiple effects [43], thus they are defined as complex [1].

Passos et al. [43] claim that " *in team sports, function performance is assured by a complex network of interpersonal relationships among players*". Since then, numerous papers that apply complex network analysis to team sports have appeared.

Two types of networks are commonly used for this kind of analysis: **passing networks** and **transition networks**.

In literature, passing networks are the most frequent ones, they are defined [43] them as a graph $G=(V,E)$ where each player is modeled as a node and two nodes v_1 and v_2 in V have a directed edge $e = (v_1, v_2)$ from v_1 to v_2 with integer weight $w(e)$ such that the player represented by node v_1 has made $w(e)$ successful passes to the player represented by node v_2 . These networks can be easily built upon event logs since sequences of passes correspond to paths within the network.

There is no formal definition of transition networks, but passes networks extended with additional nodes, that models outcomes are often referred as transition networks.

One clear limitation of these networks is that they lose both spatial and temporal information, our model instead loses only the temporal information but it keeps the spatiality.

There are many properties of passing networks that is possible to study however the most common one is *centrality*, which identify the most important nodes within a network [4].

The simplest centrality measure is the *degree centrality*, which is the number of edges incident to a node. The in-degree centrality

is simply referred as *centrality* while the out-degree centrality is referred as *prestige* [12]. Clemente et al. [13] claims that players with larger degree centrality are those who contributed with more passes to the other players of their team, while players with higher degree prestige are those to whom their teammates preferred to pass the ball more often.

Research [12, 13] showed different competitive leagues and scores had no statistical influence on the degree centrality levels of cooperation in football.

Another centrality is the *betweenness centrality* of a node, which is the number of times it lies on the shortest path between two other nodes inside the network [22]. This study [44] claims that the betweenness centrality of a player measures the impact of removing that player from the game, either by getting a red card or by being isolated by the opponent's defense.

Flow centrality, similarly to the betweenness centrality, captures the influence of a player on a match by "capturing the fraction of times that a player intervenes in paths that result in a shot" [17]. Duch et al. [17] claims that the flow centrality measures performance in a way that "sensible results that are in agreement with the subjective views of analysts and spectators".

The most sophisticated centrality measure is the **eigenvector centrality** [3]. Eigenvector centrality is defined as the principal eigenvector of the adjacency matrix that defines the network. The defining equation of an eigenvector is:

$$\text{Eigenvector centrality: } \lambda \mathbf{v} = \mathbf{A} \mathbf{v} \quad (4)$$

- \mathbf{A} is the adjacency matrix of the graph.
- λ is a constant (the eigenvalue).
- \mathbf{v} is the eigenvector.

Equation 4 lends itself to the interpretation that a node that has a high eigenvector score is one that is adjacent to nodes that are themselves high scorers.

Eigenvector centrality is derived from steady-state analysis of stochastic processes, showed in Definition 3.1, this means that graphs are treated as stochastic processes.

Definition 3.1. Given a probability space (Ω, \mathcal{F}, P) , a stochastic process is any collection of random variables defined on this probability space:

$$\{X(t) : t \in T\} \quad (5)$$

where:

- Ω is a sample space.
- \mathcal{F} is a σ – algebra.
- P is a probability measure.
- T is an index set.

Definition 3.2. If the index set T is *countable* $\{X(t) : t \in T\}$ is a **discrete-time process**, otherwise it is **continuous-time process**.

Definition 3.3. A **discrete-time stochastic process** $\{X(t) : t \in T\}$ on a countable set, T , is a **Markov chain** iff:

$$\begin{aligned} \forall i_n, \dots, i_0 \in T \text{ and } n \in \mathbb{N} \\ P\{X(n) = i_n | X(n-1) = i_{n-1}, \dots, X(0) = i_0\} \\ = P\{X(n) = i_n | X(n-1) = i_{n-1}\} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Stochastic processes are difficult to analyse and often they are simplified into **Markov chains**. This kind of processes is simpler to analyse because of the Markov property showed in Equation 6. In words, this property says: *The future is independent from the past if the present is given*. This way is possible to discard the past during the analysis.

Definition 3.4. A **stationary distribution** of a Markov chain is a probability distribution that remains unchanged in the Markov chain as time progresses. Typically, it is represented as a row vector π whose entries are probabilities summing to 1, and given transition matrix P , it satisfies:

$$\pi = \pi P \quad (7)$$

The problem of eigenvector centrality is that steady state distributions of Markov chains not always exist, thus in these particular cases, steady state analysis is indeed impossible, because, eigenvector centrality can not be derived from the steady state distribution. Markov chain that have a steady state distribution are **ergodic**, as showed in Definition 3.5.

Definition 3.5. A Markov chain is **ergodic** if it is an aperiodic Markov chain, all states of which are positive recurrent.

Markov chains that are irreducible and aperiodic are proven to be ergodic. **PageRank** [40] is a variant of eigenvector centrality that modifies the graph to ensure these two properties. PageRank was originally used on the web graph to rank web pages. To ensure irreducibility and aperiodicity PageRank uses the "teleportation step". The teleportation models the probability of jumping to any other node in the graph. Equation 8 shows the formula that PageRank uses to assign ranks. In the original paper, this equation is iterated several times over all nodes until the ranks converge to the steady state.

Let x be a node in a graph:

$$\text{PageRank}(x) = \alpha \left(\frac{1}{N} \right) + (1 - \alpha) \sum_{y \in L(x)} \frac{\text{PR}(y)}{C(y)} \quad (8)$$

where:

- $L(x)$ is the set of nodes that link to x
- $C(y)$ is the out-degree of node y
- $1 - \alpha$ is probability of random jumping to any other node in the graph (teleportation step)
- N is the total number of nodes

This study [44] claims that the PageRank measure gives each player a value that is approximately the likelihood that the player will be in possession of the ball after a fixed amount of passes. Analyzing data from the 2010 FIFA World Cup, they showed that Xavi Hernández (Spain) and Bastian Schweinsteiger (Germany) were particularly central to their teams.

In literature, most of the studies uses centrality measure to identify key players [12, 13, 17, 20, 25, 44]. These studies [12, 13], in particular, showed that there is no correlation between degree centrality and performance. Duch et al. [12] shows that there is a correlation between perceived performance and flow centrality, but their study lacks extensive testing, since they analyses only 20 games from the football 2008 UEFA European Cup. Thus, these results are inconclusive. This study [44] ranks player by means of PageRank. As explained before the PageRank of a node depends on the PageRank of his neighbors, thus PageRank of a player depends on the PageRank of his neighbors. This is a problem when ranking players, because a bad

player that plays in a good team achieves a good PageRank. A better way to rank players is to isolate them from the rest of a team, being the rank the individual ability of a player, this captures the individual contribution of such player independently from his team-mates.

Ranking individual players is out of the scope of this thesis, but the studies listed above model also team performance by aggregating (eg. summing, averaging...) ranks of individual players. These studies [18, 20] claim "The success of the teams is rarely a simple summation of the tools each individual brings. Instead, it must emerge from the dynamic interactions of the group as a whole". Thus, the best way of analyzing the team as a complex system instead of breaking splitting it and analyzing its components singularly.

Clemente et al. [13] abstracting from the players and keeping only their roles discovered that *"the fundamental statistical differences of centrality levels were found between different tactical positions"*. Pappalardo et al. [42] claim that *"In football, each role corresponds to a different area of the playing field where is assigned responsibility relative to his teammates"*.

According to [26] that analyses many approaches to analyze team sports, the graphs derived in Chapter 2 are a novel approach to analyze teams as a complex system by abstracting from the players and focusing only on their role exploiting the spatial information that they generate. The interaction between players is modeled as movements of the ball in these regions.

This approach analyses teams as complex systems evolving onto a fixed region of the space (the field) and interacting with it.

3.1 DEFINING FOOTBALL TEAMS BEHAVIOR

The goal of this analysis is to capture the behavior of football teams. Given the graphs discussed in Chapter 2 the behavior of a football team is defined as *"The way teams move the ball together with their positions and movements onto the field and the performance that they achieve"*.

The behavior defined above is very complex and can be divided into three parts. Since slightly different information (different graphs) are required to capture each part of the above defined behavior, we developed three different models:

- **Flow model:** models how football teams move the ball.

- **Density model:** models the space occupancy of a football team.
- **Score model:** models the performance of a football team.

The flow model is the simplest one because it does not take into account the opponent. It captures the way teams move the ball when they are not challenged.

Density and score model are more complex since they perform these analysis taking also into account the behavior of the rival team. To account for the behavior of both teams we provide a formal model of football games and an exact merging algorithm of the graphs modeling the two teams facing each other.

3.2 MODELING A GAME

Cotta et al. [15] define football as a game of two teams, whose networks clash. In our study, games are modeled by means of two graphs.

Given two teams A and B an entire game in which A plays against B is modeled using the graphs: $A \rightarrow B$ and $B \rightarrow A$. These graphs model respectively A attacking B and vice versa. Given the edge classification discussed in Chapter 2, offensive edges of A and defensive edges of B are used to build the graph $A \rightarrow B$. The symmetric process is used to build the graph $B \rightarrow A$. In these graphs, edges belonging to the offending team are the ones connecting different zones (no self-loops). The edges belonging to the defending team, instead are the self-loops.

3.3 FLOW MODEL

This model predicts which are the most frequent paths (called flows) that the ball takes during a game. Since there are no particular requirements about this analysis the graph discussed in Chapter 2 is used as it is. This analysis captures only the offensive behavior of a team so, the self-loops are ignored when analyzing the graph.

Algorithm 2 shows the procedure utilized to compute the flows. The algorithm is based on a modified DFS that finds only fixed length paths and it does not expand paths that are never taken. The algorithms start by creating a min heap of the specified size (line 2) then it removes all self-loops from the graph (line 2). The final step is to call the modified DFS for each node in the

Algorithm 2 flow recognition

Input:

graph graph modelling a team
length length of the paths
size number of paths

Output:

flows Predicted paths

```
1: function FLOWS(graph, length, size)
2:   paths  $\leftarrow$  minHeap(size)           ▷ create a min heap
3:                                       ▷ of the specified size
4:   remove all self-loops from graph
5:   function DFS(path, cost, count)
6:     if cost < minHeap.min() then return
7:     if count == length then
8:       minHeap.push(path)
9:       return
10:    if there is a loop then return
11:    for neighbour  $\in$  path.lastNode().neighbours() do
12:      weight  $\leftarrow$  path.lastNode().cost(neighbour)
13:      DFS(path + [node], cost * weight, count + 1)
14:    for node  $\in$  graph.nodes() do
15:      DFS([node], 1, 0)
16:    return paths
```

graph to populate the min heap (line 14-15). This modified DFS checks if the path has a chance to be taken (line 6) otherwise it stops exploring the current path. Then check if the length is reached (line 7), in that case, it adds the path to the min-heap and stops expanding (line 8-9). If there is a loop it discards the path (line 10). The last case (line 11-13) is reached only if the path has not reached the length and it has a chance to be taken. In this case, the algorithm visits all the neighbors for the last node.

3.3.1 Validation

To validate the model we use a similar procedure, to the one described in Algorithm 2, to measure the most frequent paths taken during a game. Since Algorithm 2 takes in input a graph,

games are converted in graphs that share the same nodes, thus the same spatial information, like the ones present in the model, but the edges (and their weights) are derived only from that particular game. Then Algorithm 2 is executed on this graph, and the paths predicted by the model are compared to the one measured. The two sets are compared by means of the **normalized compression distance**.

Equation 9 shows the most informative metric to compare two strings, the **normalized information distance (NID)** [10, 31]. The Kolmogorov complexity of a string x is the length, in bits, of the shortest computer program of the fixed reference computing system the produces x as output. NID, by means of the Kolmogorov complexity, discovers for every pair of strings the feature in which they are most similar and expresses that similarity on a scale from 0 to 1 [10].

Let x and y be two strings.

$$\text{NID}(x, y) = \frac{K(xy) - \min(K(x), K(y))}{\max(K(x), K(y))} \quad (9)$$

where:

- $K(x)$ is the Kolmogorov complexity of the string x .
- $K(y)$ is the Kolmogorov complexity of the string y .
- xy is the concatenation of the two strings.

Unfortunately, NID is uncomputable since the Kolmogorov complexity is uncomputable. But, Kolmogorov complexity can be approximated using data compression programs [10]. Thus, NID can be approximated by the **normalized compression distance (NCD)** [9], which is showed in Equation 10.

Let x and y be two strings.

$$\text{NCD}(x, y) = \frac{C(xy) - \min(C(x), C(y))}{\max(C(x), C(y))} \quad (10)$$

where:

- C is a compressor
- $C(x)$ is the size of the string x compressed using C
- $C(y)$ is the size of the string y compressed using C .

- xy is the concatenation of the two strings.

Since the model and the measurement return a set of sequences each, these are converted into strings and compressed by means of **gzip** to compute NCD. The parameters of this model are:

- **Subdivision**: playing area subdivision to use.
- **length**: length of the most frequent paths.
- **cut-off**: number of most frequent path returned.

3.4 DISTRIBUTION MODEL

This model predicts which are the most important regions during a game which are the ones that contain more events.

Given the game definition present in Section 3.2, in which games are modeled as two graphs $A \rightarrow B$ and $B \rightarrow A$. To compute which are the most important regions of team A we run PageRank on the graph $A \rightarrow B$ that contains the attacking pattern of team A and the defensive pattern of team B. The symmetric process is run for team B. The regions that have a higher PageRank are more important while the ones with a lower PageRank are less important.

The parameters of this model are:

- **Subdivision**: playing area subdivision to use.
- α : teleportation step probability.

3.4.1 Validation

To validate these results we measure the event distribution during a game and we compare the one measured with the one predicted by the model. The two distributions are compared by means of the **Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence** which is a measure of how one probability distribution is different from a second, reference probability distribution [30].

We developed a baseline to check if the model achieves a higher accuracy than a simple baseline. This baseline averages the distributions measured in past games of the team and compares this distribution with the one measured in the future game.

In the end, we compared the baseline with the model to check the difference in accuracy between the two to see if the added complexity results in higher accuracy.

3.5 SCORE MODEL

This model is slightly different from the other because it predicts the winner of a game. We restricted our analysis to victories/loses, because it is very difficult to take draws into account. But, they might be included in future works. The graph that it utilizes is based on the one discussed in Chapter 2 with some additional information added. This information is necessary to take into account goalkeeper and goal inside the model.

Two nodes are added to the graph: **goalkeeper** and **goal**. The goalkeeper node models the ability to block a shot, while the goal nodes model the ability to score. The goalkeeper node is connected to the midfield and the weight of the edge is given by the saves performed by the team. The goal node is connected to the goalkeeper and to the mid-field assuming that there is a kick-off after a goal. The edge connecting goal-keeper to goal accounts for the scoring capability of the attacking team. More precisely, the edge connecting the goalkeeper to mid-field and the one connecting goal to mid-field are defensive edges, while the edge connecting the goalkeeper to the goal is an offensive edge. Some regions are connected to the goalkeeper, these edges model the shots performed by the attacking team. Since shots might come from any region on the field, more than one region might be connected to the goalkeeper.

After building such graph, PageRank is used to compute the steady state of the graph $A \rightarrow B$ and $B \rightarrow A$. Then to determine the winner $P(\text{goal}(A))$ and $P(\text{goal}(B))$ from the steady state distributions are compared. $P(\text{goal}(A))$ (respectively $P(\text{goal}(B))$) represents the probability of A (respectively B) scoring; the model returns as the winner, the team that has a higher probability of scoring. Thus, if $P(\text{goal}(A))$ is greater than $P(\text{goal}(B))$ the model predicts a victory of A.

The parameters of this model are:

- **Subdivision:** playing area subdivision to use.
- α : teleportation step probability.
- **Home-boost:** boost given the team playing in home.

The previous model does not take into account the home/away factor. The study present in [41] measures the victory distribution of teams playing home and away. These results show that teams playing home have a 10% advantage over the ones playing away. To take these results into account, the HomeBoost

parameter is introduced inside the model. Further analysis of this parameter are present in Chapter 4.

3.5.1 Validation

Three baselines are derived to compare the accuracy of this model. They are based on:

- Measured distribution of victories, draws and defeats.
- Number of home or away victories.
- Bookmakers odds.

Algorithm 3 Distribution based baseline

Input:

A Home team.

B Away team.

Output:

R Predicted winner.

```
1: function PREDICT(A, B)
2:   R  $\leftarrow$   $\perp$ 
3:   x  $\leftarrow$  random number in [0, 74)
4:   if x < 48 then
5:     R  $\leftarrow$  A
6:   else
7:     R  $\leftarrow$  B
8:   return R
```

Distribution-based baseline. The study present in [41] measures victory, draw and defeat distribution on a dataset containing 6,396 games from 145 teams sampled over three seasons (2013/2014, 2014/2015, 2015/2016) of the six major European football leagues:

- Premier League
- Ligue 1
- Bundesliga
- Serie A
- La Liga

- Eredivisie

The distribution observed shows that the outcome of the game in general is:

- 48% of the times the home team wins.
- 26% of the times they draw.
- 26% of the times the away team wins.

Since the dataset used in this thesis partially overlaps with the one used in the study [41], it is assumed that the same distribution applies on both datasets.

Algorithm 3 uses this hypothesis to predict, in a very simple way, the winner of a game.

Since draws are not considered the algorithm predicts only victory and defeat. It first generates the random number x in the interval $[0, 48 + 26)$ (line 3), then if x falls in $[0, 48)$ the algorithm says that the home team is the winner. Otherwise, x will fall in the interval $[48, 74)$ and in this case it says that the away team will win.

Exploiting the distribution observed in [41] another baseline can be derived: always say home is the winner. This baseline achieves 48% of accuracy. But, this dummy baseline is not used since the baseline showed in the Algorithm 3 performs better.

Victory-based baseline. The baseline showed in Algorithm 4 predicts the winner exploiting only information about the home, away and the number of victories. This baseline is trained on the same data used to train the model, and every time a game is predicted is added to the train set. This way the game N is predicted using information about all $N - 1$ previous games. The algorithm at first generates a random number x in the interval $[0, HomeCount + AwayCount)$ (line 3) where $HomeCount$ is the number of home victories of the home team and $AwayCount$ is the number away victories of the away team. Then if x falls into the interval $[0, HomeCount)$ it says that the home team is the winner, otherwise if the x falls into $[HomeCount, HomeCount + AwayCount)$ it says that the away team is the winner.

It is worth to point out that keeping home and away victories separated instead of aggregating them allows to take into account the home and away factor.

Algorithm 4 Victory based baseline

Input:

A Home team.
B Away team.
HomeCount number of team A home victories.
AwayCount number of team B away victories.

Output:

R Predicted winner.

```
1: function PREDICT(A, B)
2:   R  $\leftarrow$   $\perp$ 
3:    $x \leftarrow$  random number in [0, HomeCount + AwayCount)
4:   if  $x <$  HomeCount then
5:     R  $\leftarrow$  A
6:   else
7:     R  $\leftarrow$  B
8:   check the real winner ▷ Fit on this new game
9:   if A won the game then
10:    HomeCount  $\leftarrow$  HomeCount + 1
11:  else
12:    AwayCount  $\leftarrow$  AwayCount + 1
13:  return R
```

Algorithm 5 Bookmakers odds baseline

Input:

A Home team.
B Away team.
Odds bookmakers betting odds.

Output:

R Predicted winner.

```
1: function PREDICT(A, B)
2:   R  $\leftarrow$   $\perp$ 
3:   if Odds[A] < Odds[B] then
4:     R  $\leftarrow$  A
5:   else
6:     R  $\leftarrow$  B
7:   return R
```

Bookmakers-odds baseline. The last baseline derived, showed in Algorithm 5, exploits the bookmakers odds. In this particular case, the data used is gathered from the bookmaker **Bet365**.

Also in this case the algorithm is very simple, given two teams A and B, it takes the Odds[A] and Odds[B] (line 3) and if Bet365 says that A is more likely to win, the baseline says A will win otherwise it says that B is the winner.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In sports science literature, most of the analyses are performed on very small and public datasets [15, 17, 44]. In the case of football, these datasets are often released by UEFA or FIFA and they are free and public available [16].

There are few exceptions like [25] that utilized a dataset containing data from 23 teams of the English Premier League, or this study [42] that analyzes a big dataset containing data from the five prominent European football leagues: Premier League, La Liga, Bundesliga, Serie A, and Ligue 1.

As discussed in Chapter 1, the dataset available for this study is the **Wyscout** dataset that contains three seasons (2014, 2015, 2016) of the Italian Serie A. In our tests, training on less than one season resulted in disconnected and poorly informative graphs. Since we have three seasons at our disposal, to exploit all of them we decided to train on two seasons (2014 and 2015) and test the models on one season (2016).

Since the physical condition is very important in sports, also players and coaches might change from one season to another, games are moved from the test set to the train set after the prediction. This way the prediction of game N relies on the $N - 1$ games played before.

Training on two seasons resulted in (almost) fully connected and informative graphs, as showed by the accuracy achieved by the models.

In all figures presented in this section, the attack direction is always intended from left to right.

4.1 PLAYING AREA SUBDIVISION

Figure 8 shows some of the regions found by means of the procedure discussed in Chapter 2. Subdivision containing from 7 to 9 regions are similar to the ones presented in this study [42] that uses a data-driven approach to cluster players. While, they are very different from hand designed [7, 24, 37] or uniform grids [2, 5, 8, 21, 36, 39, 47].

Figure 8: Example of playing area subdivisions. The field is measured in percentage and the attacking direction is from left to right.

Subdivision containing from 7 to 14 regions resembles classic roles and line-ups commonly used in football. The ones with more than 13 regions show no clear match between roles and regions.

As already discussed in Chapter 2, there are symmetric (e.g 7, 8, 9, 11, 13 regions) and asymmetric (e.g 10, 12, 14) subdivisions, where symmetric ones have the same number of regions on the left and the right side.

According to our tests, there is no correlation between this asymmetry and the accuracy of the predictions.

4.2 GRAPHS

In Chapter 3 we introduced three different models. These models are based on some variations of the same graph. To avoid redundancy and keep this section simple we decided to show only the underlying graph of score model since the other models are built on a subset of this graph.

Figure 10 shows the graph of FC Inter generated by the score model. According to our edge classification, the black edges are the attacking ones, the red edges are defensive ones. The score model is the only model that contains goalkeeper and goal node, in Figure 10 goalkeeper node is the one in the penalty, the goal node is just outside of the pitch. The goalkeeper is connected to the goal by an offensive edge which weight is the average number of goal scored in a game. Defensive goalkeeper (on the left side of Figure 10) models the defensive goalkeeper. This node is connected to mid-field and the weight of this edges is the average number of saves. Goals are connected to midfield, since in football after scoring a goal the ball is repositioned in midfield. For simplicity, the weight of this edge is set to 1, this values does not influence the analysis and can be any value since goal node has no other outgoing edge or self-loop. All other nodes are connected as explained in Chapter 2.

Flow model contains a very similar graph but it does not contain all the red (defensive) edges, goalkeeper, goal (both defensive and offensive one) and the relative edges.

Distribution model instead does not contain goal and goalkeeper nodes and the relative edges, but it contains the self-loops.

Figure 11 and 12 shows how a game between Juventus and Napoli is represented by the score model. As stated in Chapter 3 games are modeled by means of two graphs, in Figure 11 Na-

Figure 9: Playing area subdivision used to generate the graph shown below.

Figure 10: FC Inter graph generated by the model. The nodes inside the penalty are the goalkeepers, the ones outside are the goal, all the remaining nodes are the regions of the field. The attack direction is from left to right.

poli attacks Juventus and in Figure 12 Juventus attacks Napoli. Since the goalkeeper and the goal of the attacking team are not utilized they are not shown in the figure. Score model executes PageRank on both graphs, then it compares $P(\text{goal}(\text{Napoli}))$ and $P(\text{goal}(\text{Juventus}))$; the one that achieves

higher probability is considered winner by the score model.

Figure 11: Graph of Juventus attacking Napoli. The attack direction is from left to right

Figure 12: Graph of Napoli attacking Juventus. The attack direction is from left to right.

4.3 FLOW MODEL

The parameters of this model, as discussed in Chapter 3, are the length of the paths, the number of paths and the playing area subdivision. In these tests, the length of the paths is set to 5. Longer paths are preferred since they give more information

about how teams move the ball, but at the same time, the likelihood of taking a particular path is computed by the product of the likelihood of taking the single steps contained in the path. Since the likelihood of taking a step is a probability its value is between 0 and 1. Thus, the product of values that are less than one quickly drop to zero.

Paths longer than 5 achieve very low probabilities that they are almost impossible to be taken.

As described in Section 3.3.1 we validate this model by comparing the NCD similarity between the flows predicted and the ones measured during the game taken into analysis. Figure 13

Figure 13: Accuracy of flows of length 5 by varying the subdivision

shows the NCD similarity by varying the number of regions inside the playing area subdivision. Since the model predicts the flows that are more likely to be taken during the game, the comparison is between the predicted flows and the ones measured during the games analyzed. Games contain 1700 events in average generated by two teams, so each team generates roughly 850 events. Since the reference flows are measured one game at the time, subdivisions with more than 23 zones contain some of them with no events. Therefore there is not enough data to perform analysis on more than 23 zones.

Figure 13 shows that the NCD increases by increasing the number of zones, the most accurate subdivision is the one with 21 zones, achieving an NCD similarity of 75%. The model seems

to capture more information by increasing the number of zones, thus more zones lead to better results.

Figure 14 shows that the NCD is almost the same between

Figure 14: Accuracy achieved on different teams

all teams. It is interesting that the most unpredictable team is Napoli. In 2016, Napoli was known for being one of the most fun teams to watch and according to these results, the cause might be the unpredictable play-style of Napoli that surprises the spectator.

These results, with Juventus and Napoli being the most unpredictable teams match the results obtained in this study [11] that correlates entropy of networks with the performance of football teams.

Figure 15 shows that the NCD is consistent during all season with very small variations observed. In average, the NCD is about 73%. It is worth to point out, that this model does not take the adversary into account to perform this prediction. Since teams try to disrupt each other line paths, our tests show that they succeed in disrupting about 30% of the flows.

Figure 15: Accuracy measured during 2016 season of the Italian Serie A

4.4 DISTRIBUTION MODEL

This model predicts the events distribution. The first parameter tested is alpha, which controls the teleportation probability. As described in Section 3.4.1 we compare the distribution predicted by the model with the ones measured during games by means of the KL divergence.

In our tests, the variation alpha leads to almost imperceptible variations in KL divergence. Given these results, we decided to use the default value of alpha that corresponds to 0.85. Since this value corresponds to the average pass success rate measured in football games.

Figure 16 shows that by increasing the number of zones the KL divergence slightly diminishes. This is expected because from one side the model becomes more informative, but on the other side, the number of variables contained in the distribution increases too, making the problem more difficult.

In all distribution, the KL divergence is higher than 92% with some peaks of 96% achieved with subdivisions containing 4 to 8 zones.

Figure 17 shows that there are small variations in KL divergence between different teams. All teams achieves an accuracy grater than 0.90, with Torino being the most predictable with

Figure 16: KL divergence measured by varying the number of zones

0.96 of KL divergence. Napoli is the most unpredictable team achieving the lowest score of 0.90.

Figure 18 shows that KL divergence is consistent during all season, with very small variations measured.

Figure 19 compares the model with the baseline described in Chapter 3 which averages the distributions measured in past games of the team and compares these averages with the distributions measured in the future games.

The baseline shows slightly better accuracy than the model and is also is more consistent.

Since the baseline does not take the adversary into account, it seems that the events distributions are not influenced by the adversary, each team maintains the strong identity given by the lineups, and the way of playing is preserved during games independently from the adversary.

Figure 20 shows a heat-map generated from the distribution of the game Roma-Lazio predicted by the model. From these heat maps can be noted that Rome has a more even distribution, and both teams prefer to play on the left side on the field.

The difference between the heat-maps is very subtle but, in this game, at least one characteristic of the play-style of these two teams might be observed; Lazio jumps from defense to attack by skipping the midfield more often than Rome.

Figure 17: KL divergence measured on each team

Figure 18: KL divergence measured during the 2016 season of the Italian Serie A

Figure 19: The KL divergence of the model compared to the baseline by varying the number of zones

(a) Roma in possession of the ball

(b) Lazio in possession of the ball

Figure 20: Distribution of the game Roma-Lazio predicted by the model.

4.5 SCORE MODEL

This model captures the performance of the teams by predicting the winner of the game.

In this case, each team is modeled by data taken from two seasons. This amount of data is enough to use subdivisions containing up to 42 zones. After 42 zones even with data taken from two different seasons is not enough, there are some zones with very few or no events at all which make the comparison impossible.

As described in Section 3.5.1 this model is validated against the real outcome of the games and some baselines. The distribution baseline utilizes the distribution of wins and loss measured in the five major European football leagues to guess the winner of football games. The victory baseline uses the number of victories of the two teams. The bookmaker baseline uses the odds given by the bookmakers.

The first parameter tested is the HomeBoost. According to this study [41], teams playing in home have a 10% advantage over the other teams. Figure 21 shows the analysis performed to validate that 10% is the correct value.

The second parameter tested is alpha. Figure 22 shows that

Figure 21: Accuracy measured by varying home boost, the pitch is divided in 38 regions. The alpha of teleportation step is fixed to 0.85.

Figure 22: Accuracy measured varying the teleportation probability

the maximum accuracy is achieved with alpha between 73 and 89. Since alpha models the probability of the ball being thrown away, these values match the average pass success rate measured during games.

In the remaining tests we decided to set alpha to its default value of 0.85.

Figure 23 shows the accuracy measured by varying the playing area subdivision. Increasing the number of zones leads to higher accuracy, because the model captures more information. The best accuracy is measured with the subdivision shown in Figure 24, which divides the field in 38 zones.

Figure 25 shows teams home and away accuracy. The model achieves similar accuracy in both cases. These results show that teams that have very consistent performance (according to the dataset) achieve an higher accuracy. In particular, in season 2016 Juventus won almost every game played in home and the model correctly predicted each one of them.

To check if the added complexity to the model gives an advantage with respect to simpler baselines, we compared the score model with the baselines described in Chapter 3. The model showed a higher accuracy of almost 10% respect for the best baseline.

Figure 23: Accuracy measured varying the number of zones (nodes)

Figure 24: Subdivision containing 38 zones

(a) Home accuracy

(b) Away accuracy

Figure 25: Home and away accuracy for each team.

Figure 26: Comparison between model and baseline accuracy. On the x-axis, there are championship days. On the y-axis, there is the average accuracy measured until that moment. They are not 38 because some championships days are spread over more than one actual day.

CONCLUSIONS

The goal of this thesis is to build an automated framework to model and analyze football teams. Teams are groups of individuals working together towards a common goal. This framework models football teams via a stochastic representation. We implemented this representation via a weighted graph that captures the interactions between the players.

Moreover, the graph implementation gives several advantages. It is easy to interpret, visualize, analyze, and allows to use the huge amount of graph algorithms present in the literature.

Other approaches model teams by aggregating their components, losing the information about the collaboration between the players.

The framework contains three models that analyze different issues of the behavior of football teams.

The flow model predicts the most common sequences of passes of football teams. This model achieves an accuracy of more than 72% when compared to the passes actually made by the teams. The limitation of this model is that it does not take the adversary into account since the predictions are made exploiting only the data of the teams taken in isolation.

The distribution model predicts the distribution of events during a game. This model predicts the distribution using data of two teams facing each other in the game. But, when compared to a baseline that does not account for the opposing team, it showed a lower accuracy.

The score model predicts the winner of the game exploiting the data of the two teams playing against each other. This model showed an accuracy of 72%, outperforming by more than 10% the predictions made by the bookmakers.

The predictions of the score model are limited since it can not predict all possible outcomes of football games, in particular, it does not predict draws.

FURTHER IMPROVEMENTS

There are several improvements that can be performed on the models proposed in this thesis.

Games are modeled by means of two graphs, we believe that merging these two graphs into a more complex one might lead to a more interpretable model that better captures how networks clash into each other during a game.

Another possible improvement, to take the home factor into account, is to derive two graphs for each team; a home graph that models only games played in home and an away graph modeled with all the games played away.

When comparing two teams, the home graph of the team playing home and the away one of the other team should be used. This way the model is sensitive behavioral differences of the teams when playing home or away. Moreover, this difference might change over time, and the two graphs approach might adapt to it by itself.

Our models lose the temporal information contained in the dataset. Since the physical condition is very important in sports; adding this information to the models might improve their accuracy.

The improvements discussed above can be applied to all the models proposed. One limitation, specific to the flow model is that it does not take the adversary into account.

The score model does not predict draws, thus this model can be extended to take also this case into account.

In developing the flow model we tried to use the Viterbi's algorithm [52] and the Dijkstra's algorithm. These algorithms failed to recognize sequences that end in nodes already visited. To also take these sequences into account we developed the Algorithm 2. The graph representation of the flow model is unable to take the opposing team into account. Developing a different one that can take into account both teams might improve the accuracy of the model.

In the literature, there are some studies that try to identify the most frequent sequence of passes, but our results are not comparable to most of the studies, because they analyze passes between players. In this thesis, we abstract from players and analyze only passes between different zones.

This study by Van Haaren et al. [51] uses inductive logic programming to find patterns in offensive football strategies. Their result is a set of rules that describe sequences of passes between different zones of the football pitch. This study uses a different subdivision of the football field, thus the results are not directly comparable with the sequences predicted by the flow model. In the future, we would like to implement their algorithm and execute it on our dataset to compare the results.

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